

Kansei Analysis of Pattern Design

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Abstract: Patterns are exhibited via different media in our daily life. People can see patterns from clothes, bags, wallpapers and even the facade of architectures. Pattern design can beautify and characterize the products. Some patterns have become the representation of a brand, such as the checkered patterns on the products of Burberry. Designers create patterns by using units along with grid or frame systems. Hence, patterns can vary in thousands of visual forms and convey various images. People tend to evoke different emotions while perceiving different style of patterns. The main purpose of this study was set to figure out the relationships between pattern design and people's Kansei evaluation. Kansei analysis was used in the study. A construction framework for patterns generation was defined and then, the test samples were created. 30 subjects were asked to estimate the 81 pattern samples with 6 Kansei adjectives which were picked out via KJ method. The 6 phrases are glorious, natural, classical, modest, rhythmic and joyful. 9-level Likert scale was adopted to record the evaluation. Then, the data were analyzed by Quantification Theory Type I. The results included a formula for pattern design to designers. Designers can follow the rules to create new patterns. We hope they can help designers to create patterns more effectively in products or graphic design. And consumers can also grasp the features of the products via the pattern style exhibited on the packaging easier.

Key words: Kansei Engineering, Pattern Design, Visual Kansei, Quantification Theory Type I.

1. Introduction

Patterns occurred on utensils since the Medieval Ages. Now, they are also used extensively in our daily life, such as in bags, clothes, and wallpapers. Visual patterns are very common such as simple decorative patterns (stripes, zigzags, and polka-dots). With different materials and arrangement, patterns can be varied in many different styles. Products with pattern design become more charming and characteristic. Some patterns even became the representative of countries or culture. For instance, people associate the sakura pattern with Japan, and dragon figure with China. In recent years, the traditional cloth with red flower also became a beautiful image of Taiwan. Taiwanese remind the days in 1950s when seeing the pattern of red flowers such as peony. The patterns not only show different cultures, but also convey different meanings and images, like peace or love.

In the five senses, our vision is the most immediate way which can receive external messages quickly. When we

see graphics or patterns, some feelings are produced in our mind. The feelings are not the same all the time. People may feel romantic with the heart pattern, and feel peace with the dove pattern. According to the different figures, arrangements or colors, patterns can be shown in various ways. People’s life is enriched by the different kinds of patterns. In addition, more people buy or use products with beautiful patterns. The brand “Burberry” are famous with the bags which are decorated by cherry patterns. The cherry patterns with red color attract many consumers, especially young group. The reason why people buy and use this kind of products is not only for the brand, but also for the design. Hence, the main purpose of this study was to figure out the main factors of pattern design which let people feel different. The results offered a rule of pattern design that designers can follow it in the future.

2. Literature Review

A pattern, from the French patron, is a type of theme of recurring events or objects, sometimes referred to as elements of a set. These elements repeat in a predictable manner [1]. The forms of patterns are variable. Researchers have their own method to classify the different form of patterns in math or in visual design. Each literature has his different value. Archbald H. Christie (1969) thinks that pattern is a design which is created by more than one figure and arranged in order. Patterns can vary many different styles by different figures or motifs. He classified patterns in four types. The four types are straight striped patterns, waved and chevron striped patterns, cross-band patterns and interlaced with counterchanged cross-band patterns. Figure1 shows the 4 types [2]. Peter Phillips and Gillian Bunce (1993) mentioned that the appearance of the repeated pattern which can be traced back to Gothic age and Victorian era. The pattern was used in decoration widely. They also said that a good pattern should be beautiful, imaginable and ordered. Their research was focused on repeated patterns and they classified them in 9 types. The 9 types are block repeats, drop repeats, brick repeats, irregular repeats, composite repeats, sateen repeats, counterchanged repeats, woodblock repeats, scale and gradation. Figure2 shows the 9 different types of repeated patterns [3]. Wu- Xie Wang (1985) presented that the form of a pattern can be separated to two parts, one is the motif or figure and the other one is the grid or frame. The motif is the unit which repeats regularly or irregularly. The unit arranges along the frame [4]. Figure3 shows the composition of a pattern.

Figure.1 Archbald H. Christie’s definition of pattern (1969)

Figure.2 Peter Phillips and Gillian Bunce's definition of repeated pattern (1993)

Figure.3 The definition of the frame and unit by Wu- Xie Wang

Every pattern has special feature and design. People will evoke different emotions while perceiving different style of patterns. The purpose of the research is to find the design factors of patterns which make people feel different. Kansei Engineering was used in the study. This technique involves determining which sensory attributes elicit particular subjective responses from people, and then designing a product using the attributes which elicit the desired responses. Chun-Juei Chou (2001) created a multi-kansei image based on formal features. The research tried to construct the corresponding relationship between Kansei vocabularies and form from a viewpoint of formal features [5]. Yuan-Ping Kao (2002) discussed the formations of product image and its relationships to music performance based on the framework of Kansei Engineering approach. Researchers not only discussed the form but also compared the relation between visual design and other senses [6]. More and more studies focus on emotional design. Nowadays, form follows not only function but also should be related to the human's emotion.

3. Experiment

3.1. The form of regular pattern

Pattern is composed by the frame and the repeated unit. The frame controls the rhythm of a pattern. The main design factors also included the size and the direction of the unit. According to the collection of patterns, there are various styles of patterns. It's not easy to define all patterns. Hence, we discussed regular patterns in the study. The frame of the regular patterns is vertical and horizontal. The unit was set to 9 types of figures (Figure 4). They are circle, triangle, square, multiple-geometry, abstract and organic figure, the figure of human, animal figure, vegetation and goods. Other definitions were listed in the Table1 below :

Figure.4 The 9 figures of unit

Table 1. Form generation of regular pattern

Item		Category
frame		Vertical-horizontal
axis	X	(1) 1/3 (2) 1/5 (3) 1/7 (4) 1/3-1/7
	Y	(1) 1/3 (2) 1/5 (3) 1/7 (4) 1/3-1/7
Figure of unit		Geometric figure : (1) Circle (2) triangle (3) square (4) multiple-geometry Non-geometric figure : (5) abstract and organic (6) human (7) animal (8) vegetation (9) goods
Size of unit (measured in the frame)		Repeat size : (1) 100% (2) 75% (3) 50% Interlace size : (4) 100% + 75% (5) 100% + 50% (6) 100% + 25% Change size gradually : (7) 100%~25% (8) 100%~50%
Form of unit		(1) repeat shape (2) similar shape (3) change shape gradually (4) special shape
Direction of unit		(1) repeat direction (2) vertically interweaved (3) horizontally interweaved (4) diagonal interweaved

The frame is divided into X axis and Y axis. When the value of X axis and Y axis is 1/3, the pattern is with the frame of 3 by 3 grids. The grid is set from 3x3 to 7x7. The pattern would show different density with diverse frames. The unit is set for geometric and non-geometric parts. The size of unit is also an important factor in pattern design. We set size in three different levels. The size or shape of the unit which is the same all the time in the pattern or they change gradually is considered as well. The direction of unit is defined for 4 different ways.

3.2. Experimental samples

According to the 33 categories of pattern design defined in the last stage, the 33 data is keyed in SPSS to do design of experiments (DOE). 16 different frames of patterns were defined (Figure 5). Hence, 81 different combination of pattern design was obtained by the results of design of experiments method. Based on the results, we drew the new patterns as the samples for the main experiment. In order to pick out the main design factors, the samples were without color. The subjects could focus on the design features, and they wouldn't be affected by the color during the experiment. The 81 samples were set in the same size. Each sample was made in 90mmx90mm card. Finally, 81 cards of pattern samples were done (Figure 6).

Figure.5 The 16 frames of patterns

Figure.6 The sample of experiment card

3.3. Pick out the experimental phrases

There are many adjectives which can describe patterns. In the study, we collected 200 phrases from books and websites. In order to reduce the numbers of phrases and picked the main adjectives, we used questionnaire survey and KJ method. The participants were 50 people with the background of design. They were asked to choose the most suitable phrases for describing patterns from the 200 phrases. As a result, 88 phrases with votes in the stage of questionnaire survey were picked. Because 88 phrases were too much for the experiment, the 88 phrases were selected by KJ method again by 5 masters with design background. The KJ method is a group process for establishing priority. At first, the 5 masters grouped the similar phrases (Figure 7). Then they named each group by using second color of sticky notes. The next step is to vote for the most important groups. When the masters have finished this step, every participant would have democratically shared their opinion on the most important groups. Once everyone has marked their votes, and ordered them by the number of votes each sticky received, with the highest numbers at the top. Finally, five Kansei adjectives and the phrases were decided, they are glorious, natural, classical, modest and rhythmic. In addition, we added the phrase “joyful” in order to know what kind of patterns do people like more.

Figure.7 Select main phrases in KJ method

3.4. Kansei experiment

Kansei is a Japanese term which means psychological feeling or image of a product. Kansei engineering refers to the translation of consumers' psychological feeling about a product into perceptual design elements. Kansei engineering is also sometimes referred to as "sensory engineering" or "emotional usability". In the experiment,

participants were 30 master students of National Cheng Kung University, with average 25 years old and design background for years. The experiment took place in the laboratory of department of Industrial Design in NCKU. The subjects were asked to group the 81 sample cards of patterns into 9 levels for each phrase (Figure 8). Each group has its own score. Arranging them from the higher score to the lower score. The highest score is 9, and the lowest score is 1. Every participant did 9-levels Likert scale 6 times for 6 phrases . After the Kansei experiment, the subjects were also asked to write an open questionnaire and fill in their personal information.

Figure.8 The subject grouped the 81 pattern samples by 9-level Likert scale

4. Results

The items and categories of pattern design and the results of experiment were analyzed by Quantification Theory Type I. The results were about the relationship between adjectives and the design factors of pattern. The results offered two aspects of the pattern design, one is about the design items and the other one is about the design categories. Designers can follow the information about the design factors which are referred to a feelings or image. The relation between each phrase and design detail and the results of questionnaire are mentioned below :

(1) Modest

The results showed the Y axis is the main factor which has strong relation with the phrase “modest”. It means that people are influenced by the density of Y axis of a pattern when they think of modest. Moreover, the dense Y axis is related to the image of modest. People think the modest pattern should be with small unit and the unit arranged regularly (Figure 9). It looks simple, ordered and without any variation. Besides, the form of unit has nothing to do with the modest pattern. The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 2.

Figure.9 The sample of modest pattern

Table 2. The results of modest pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
Y axis	1. 1/3	-0.280417	0.8235818	(the highest value)
	2. 1/5	0.5528736		
	3. 1/7	0.9371009		
	4. 1/3~1/7	-1.069349		
Form of unit	1. repeat shape	-0.073691	0.2276607	(the lowest value)
	2. similar shape	-0.062261		
	3. change shape gradually	-0.048595		
	4. special shape	0.2213921		

(2) Glorious

The results showed that the figure of unit is the key factor related to the image of glorious. It means that a pattern is glorious or not glorious which depends on the figure of the pattern. The figure of unit should be complex and occupy the full frame (Figure 10). The direction of unit has no relation with the image of glorious. The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 3.

Figure.10 The sample of glorious pattern

Table 3. The results of glorious pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
Figure of unit	1. circle	-1.061941	0.8664237	(the highest value)
	2. triangle	-1.339719		
	3. square	-1.185951		
	4. multiple-geometry	1.434355		
	5. abstract and organic	1.0936143		
	6. human	0.834355		
	7. animal	0.297318		
	8. vegetation	0.5936143		
	9. goods	-0.665645		
Direction of unit	1. repeat direction	-0.03725	0.1694967	(the lowest value)
	2. vertically interweaved	-0.035057		
	3. horizontally interweaved	-0.091571		
	4. diagonal interweaved	0.1825032		

(3) Rhythmic

In the six design items, the size of unit is the key point which makes a pattern rhythmic. The results also showed that the pattern seems to be rhythmic when the size of unit changes gradually (Figure 11). If designers want to create a rhythmic pattern, it is the basic way that changes the size of unit regularly and especially from 100%~50%. The direction of unit has little effect on the image of rhythmic. The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 4.

Figure.11 The sample of rhythmic pattern

Table 4. The results of rhythmic pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
Size of unit	1. 100%	-0.541493	0.5696309	(the highest value)
	2. 75%	-0.619271		
	3. 50%	-0.545197		
	4. 100%+75%	0.0510998		
	5. 100%+50%	0.3029516		
	6. 100%+25%	0.1029516		
	7. 100%~25%	0.7504612		
	8. 100%~50%	1.0399886		
Direction of unit	1. repeat direction	-0.06495	0.16202	(the lowest value)
	2. vertically interweaved	0.0788775		
	3. horizontally interweaved	-0.180382		
	4. diagonal interweaved	0.1989286		

(4) Classical

The figure of unit in a pattern has great effect on the image of classical, especially the figure of vegetation or plants. People think of classical pattern is with the figure of flowers or plants (Figure 12). The results may be traced back hundreds years ago. At that time, the motif of flowers or plants was a common decoration on people's appliances. In addition, the unit should be in order and placed regularly as well. The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 5.

Figure.12 The sample of classic pattern

Table 5. The results of classical pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
Figure of unit	1. circle	0.0186746	0.9379363	(the highest value)
	2. triangle	0.0513694		
	3. square	-0.285668		
	4. multiple-geometry	-0.059742		
	5. abstract and organic	0.280999		
	6. human	-1.141223		
	7. animal	-0.67826		
	8. vegetation	2.343962		
	9. goods	-0.530112		
Direction of unit	1. repeat direction	0.0513694	0.2462275	(the lowest value)
	2. vertically interweaved	0.0828509		
	3. horizontally interweaved	-0.00789		
	4. diagonal interweaved	-0.152015		

(5) Natural

The figure of unit has more relation with the image of natural than other design items. In addition, it is the figure of flowers and plants or animals that make people feel a pattern natural. The unit should be arranged irregularly and not so straight (Figure 13). The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 6.

Figure.13 The sample of natural pattern

Table 6. The results of natural pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
X axis	1. 1/3	0.0187598	0.0459597	(the lowest value)

	2. 1/5	-0.013914		
	3. 1/7	0.0009011		
	4. 1/3~1/7	-0.015127		
Figure of unit	1. circle	-0.712062	0.9691764	(the highest value)
	2. triangle	-0.975153		
	3. square	-1.304654		
	4. multiple-geometry	-0.977451		
	5. abstract and organic	0.5175678		
	6. human	0.4953455		
	7. animal	1.7990492		
	8. vegetation	2.2175678		
	9. goods	-1.06021		

(6) Joyful

The results showed that people prefer to the pattern with more rows in Y axis (Figure 14). It may be related to the image of modest. There is no absolute style that all people like. The results of Quantification Theory Type I show on Table 7.

Figure.14 The sample of joyful pattern

Table 7. The results of joyful pattern in Quantification Theory Type I (abstract)

Item	Category	Category value	Partial correlation coefficient	
Y axis	1. 1/3	-0.187924	0.6625156	(the highest value)
	2. 1/5	0.3231233		
	3. 1/7	0.4682702		
	4. 1/3~1/7	-0.509508		
Form of unit	1. repeat shape	0.1554562	0.2953983	(the lowest value)
	2. similar shape	-0.135497		
	3. change shape gradually	-0.144693		
	4. special shape	0.0470058		

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The study focused on the relationship between pattern design and Kansei phrases. With series of Kansei evaluation and the analysis of Quantification Theory Type I, the interesting relationships could be examined. Based on the results, a system of pattern design related to Kansei or emotional image can be built. In addition, designers could also follow the rules to create patterns for people's needs.

The results can also be used in interior, packaging and textile design. For interior design, designers will know how to create modest or classical wallpaper by designing different unit and frame then arranging them in right way. People can have much more comfortable environment with better visual or graphic design. The graphic or pattern on the packaging can be a symbol of a brand. The company can follow the results or use the method of Kansei Engineering to create patterns which match the image or spirit of the brand identity. For fashion design, designers can create different styles of patterns for different groups. People will wear the clothes with the right patterns which match and show their characters or personalities. In conclusion, patterns should be created with emotion inside and used in right place.

In the limit of time and effort, some basic rules, the form generation of pattern design were still constructed. It is also the hardest part to define all patterns during the study. The unit and frame are combined in many different and various ways. The results can still be improved. There are many parts of pattern design to be discussed such as irregular patterns and color usage, which may be interested in further study.

6. References

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